

Lab protocols to study Solute Carrier Transporters

Large Scale Transduction of Expi293F Cells with BacMam Virus

ID: SP000X-5

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Protocol description

This protocol is used to first produce large quantities of the BacMam virus using Sf9 cells. The viral preparation is then used to transduce Expi293F cells (host expression system for SLC transporters). Upon transduction the Expi293F cells start expressing the transporter which can then be purified from the cells.

Materials

Biological materials:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Sf9 cells in Sf-900™ II SFM (ThermoFisher Scientific Inc., Catalogue Number: 11496-015)▪ Expi293F™ Cells (ThermoFisher Scientific Inc., catalog Number: A14528)
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Sf-900™ II SFM (ThermoFisher, catalog number: 10902-104)▪ FreeStyle™ 293 Expression Medium (ThermoFisher, catalog number: 12338-018)▪ Penicillin-Streptomycin (10,000 U/mL) (ThermoFisher, catalog number: 15140-122)▪ Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), (ThermoFischer, catalog number 10500064)▪ PEG10,000 (Sigma-Aldrich, catalog number 81280)▪ 2 L vented roller bottles (Avidity Science, catalog number: TCB022002) or 3L Erlenmeyer flask- non-baffled, smooth bottom
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Microbiological Safety Cabinet - Class II▪ INFORS Multitron Cell CO2 shaker incubator or INFORS Celltron shaker placed inside a static CO2 incubator

Reagents setup

1. 1 M Sodium Butyrate prepared in PBS and filter-sterilised
2. PEG solution: 20% PEG 10,000, 0.2 M NaCl (autoclaved)

Procedure

▪ Part A of protocol

Viral preparation:

1. Prepare P2 virus stock by infecting 50 ml of Sf9 cells (2×10^6 cells/mL), grown in Sf-900 II SFM medium supplemented with 2% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), with 250 μ L of P1 virus stock as prepared previously.
2. Harvest P2 virus stock after 66 - 72 hours by centrifugation at $1,500 \times g$ for 20 minutes and store at 4°C, protected from light.
3. Add 3-10% v/v P2 viral stock to the Sf9 cells.

4. After 72 hours, centrifuge at 1,500 x *g* for 20 min and harvest P3 virus by collecting the supernatant and store at 4°C, protected from light.

▪ **Part B of protocol**

Transduction:

1. Scale up required volume of Expi293F cells in FreeStyle293 medium.
2. Dilute Expi293F cells to 1 x 10⁶ cells/mL and grow for 24 hours (at 170 rpm for 2 L roller bottles and 105 rpm for 3 L roller bottles).
3. Add 30 mL of P3 virus per litre of cells and add 5 mM sodium butyrate. Incubate cells at 37°C for 48 hours or alternatively at 30°C for 72 h.
4. After the incubation period, observe cells under the microscope to check for microbial contamination and cell viability.
5. Harvest cells by centrifugation at 1,500 x *g* for 20 min.
6. Snap freeze the cell pellets in liquid nitrogen and store at -80°C until purification.

Additional notes

Data availability

References

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.